

LCA of Carbon fibers: an analysis of available data sets

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EPFL PAN based carbon fibers- analysis of various data sets

Aims of this presentation:

- Present available data on LCI/LCA of carbon fibers, as found in literature and databases.
- Discuss potential reasons for the large differences.

Expected outcome :

- - Reach a better understanding of the disparity in LCI/LCIA data for carbon fibers
- ... and hopefully take a step towards a more “harmonized” data set for LCI/LCIA of carbon fibers

LCA of carbon fibers – observation from users

	CO ₂ footprint (kg CO ₂ eq/kg)	Energy (MJ/kg)	Reference	Year
EUCIA old	39	771	1	2022
EUCIA new	49	1041	2	2022
JCMA (2009)	22.4	967	3	2009
Das	31	704	7	2011
Duflou	55.8	1169	8	2009
Witik	54.8	1122	9	2011
Romaniw		225	10	2013
IDEMAT	12.2	339	11	2006
JCMA (2022)	20	350.2	6	2022
Ghosh		461	12	2021
JEC observer		198-594	5	2020
Der		4436 +1150	13	2021
ADEME	41	750	4	2022
Aerocomposites		478	14	2009
Bell, Pickering		171	17	2002
METI		286	15	2004
Deng		704	16	2014

Non exhaustive summary of available data from literature or databases, for 1 kg of Carbon fiber (from PAN precursor) – References are given at the end of the presentation.

Energy demand reported towards publication date

Even in recent data sets, the variation in energy demand varies by a factor 6, which value should we use in the analysis of composite manufacturing?

Carbon fiber manufacturing

Carbon Fiber **PRODUCT LCI** as input to further LCIA of composite “life cycle”

LCI for 1 kg of Carbon Fiber

CF PRODUCTION

Raw materials

Heat provided by
natural gas, fuel...

Electricity

Steam etc...

Any other input ...

AN production

PAN polymerization &
fiber

OXIDATION

CARBONISATION

SURFACE TREATMENT

COMPOSITE PART MANUFACTURING

COMPOSITE PART USE PHASE

COMPOSITE PART RECYCLING

EPFL LCA of carbon fibers – reasons for discrepancy

- Various assumptions in the manufacturing conditions, temperature, duration of each step, conversion rate from PAN to CF lead to different results.
- Various assumptions in the energy mix, the energy flow in the factory, system boundaries, type of process, geographical location, etc... due to lack of measured data and consensus in the calculation methodology.
- Data measured from lab-scale facilities may overestimate the impact, as these are not as efficient as industrial production which is confidential.
- Calculation methods may be different between researchers.

We focus here on **Cumulative Energy Demand (CED)**, for the production of 1kg of PAN based fiber (T300-700 type). This represents the total quantity of primary energy (renewable and non-renewable) used during the whole of a product's life cycle.

CED is useful as part of an LCA because it can function as a proxy for greenhouse gas emissions and other environmental impacts caused by energy use.

We focus also on the **comparison of two data sets** from JCMA and EUCIA which are industrial associations.

First data reported in 1999

- First data on “**environmental load of carbon fibre production**” by prof. Jun Takahashi, *in collaboration with Japanese carbon fiber manufacturing companies*
- Focused on **four major impact categories**:

	Energy (MJ/kg-CF)	CO ₂ (kg/kg-CF)	SO _x (kg/kg-CF)	NO _x (kg/kg-CF)
First data in 1999	478.5	29.7	0.068	2.009
Recalculated data in 2004	285.9	20.5	0.02	0.146
Recalculated data in 2009	286	22.4	0.019	0.121

European Composite industries association data on CF (2018)

Methods used:	
1. Cumulative energy demand	
2. Greenhouse Gas Protocol V1.01 / C02 eq (kg)	
3. ILCD 2011 Midpoint+ V1.06 / EU27 2010, equal weighting	

Eco footprint carbon fiber

CED 771 MJ/kg
GHG 38,9 kg CO2eq

AN				Conversion %	PAN				Conversion %	PAN input CF	CF			Delta PAN/CF	
Source...		Data	Unit		Source...	Data	Unit			Source...		Data	Unit	Data	Unit
Ecoinvent	CED	82,24264	MJ	N/A	ELCD	115,3003	MJ	53%	217,55	Literature	CED	770,9	MJ	553,34	MJ
Ecoinvent	GHG	2,821385	kg	N/A	ELCD	5,683081	kg	53%	1,07E+01	Literature	GHG	38,9	kg	2,82E+01	kg

- First mention end 2018 (@ *Composites Europe - Novembre 8, 2018*)
- *Data on CED and GHG are much higher than Japanese data*
- According to the presentation (see also: Background report, Version 1.3, p.27-30, 16/10/2018)
 - Industry input sought for, but **not obtained**
 - Eco invent & Literature Data
 - KULeuven: Duflou JR, De Moor J, Verpoest I, Dewulf W. Environmental impact analysis of composite use in car manufacturing. *Cirp Annals-Manufacturing Technology*. 2009;58(1):9-12 ... **However, only “ecopoint data” in this paper, no data on energy ,**
 - ORNL: Das S. Life cycle assessment of carbon fiber-reinforced polymer composites. *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 2011. p. 268-82.

European Composite industries association data on CF (2020)

- 20 Febr 2020: “EuCIA announces addition of new carbon fibre data to Eco Impact Calculator” (<http://www.jeccomposites.com/knowledge/international-composites-news/eucia-announces-addition-new-carbon-fibre-data-eco-impact>)
 - *“In a recent cooperation, **experiment-based data** produced by the **Institut für Textiltechnik (ITA) of RWTH Aachen University, Germany**, and EuCIA’s study were thoroughly reviewed and **EuCIA’s initial LCA data** adjusted to reflect actual experience of the PAN to carbon fibre conversion efficiency. Both data sets, initial and new, are now available to Eco Calculator users.”*

	Carbon footprint (kgCO ₂ /kg CF)	Cumulative Energy Demand (MJ/kgCF)
Initial data (2018)	38.9	770.9
New data (2020)	49.0	1040.9

First presented by **prof. Jun Takahashi**, The University of Tokyo, Japan during ECCM20 (June 29, 2022)

Published end October 2022 by **The Japan Carbon Fiber Manufacturers Association (JCMA)**

<https://www.carbonfiber.gr.jp/english/index.html> or [Lifecycle Assessment Model \(carbonfiber.gr.jp\)](#)

CED: 350 MJ/kg-CF (including 32 MJ as feedstock energy)

GHG: 19.8 kg-CO₂/kg-CF

SO_x: 0.016 kg-SO_x/kg-CF

NO_x: 0.035 kg-NO_x/kg-CF

- Similar approach (feedstock energy is included in both).
- **EUCIA** (998MJ more recent estimate, 2022) uses a mix of data based on
 - measurements in laboratories and pilot lines
 - theoretical estimations, data from validated but not transparent databases
 - available (literature) data

... because they could not obtain data directly from carbon fibre manufacturers.
- **JCMA** (350 MJ) uses data aggregated from the 3 main CF manufacturers (Toray, Mitsubishi Chemical, Teijin), in 2017
 - measurements in factories during CF production of 6994 tons of CF
 - Aggregation to respect confidentiality, so not all data is clearly available.

Reasons for discrepancy (tentative)

Energy related to electricity use is very different, and should be clarified:

- **EUCIA**: electricity (Europe market) for oxidation/carbonization: 496MJ, and energy for production of PAN fiber is 323MJ (not sure if all is electricity!), leading to 500-800MJ, depending on the part of electricity in PAN production.
- **JCMA**: electricity for process is 92.7MJ (external and internally generated), the rest comes from fuel, natural gas, etc. Hence electricity represents only 25-30% of the energy use for making CF, and much more in EUCIA data.

Other difference: **economy of scale** is crucial, for example heat recuperation is very effective in large scale production facilities, whereas not done in pilot lines.

The differences between EUCIA and JCMA data sets is most probably due to large **differences in input data**:

- Industrial versus lab-scale and pilot plant data, and theoretical assumptions.
- Large difference in electricity consumption, possibly due to heat recuperation and energy efficiency increased in industrial versus lab-scale, and difficulty to compare datasets (separation of PAN production or not).

Still, there is an **urgent need** for

- **critically analysing all** published data
- creating a 'harmonised' CED/LCIA-data set , based on **industrial reality**
- performing a **sensitivity study** on the most important parameters (type of CF, type of precursor, used energy inputs, ...)
- further broaden the discussion from **CED** to **all impact categories** → **full LCIA**
- Meetings are ongoing to better compare the datasets and understand these differences

Contributions from JCMA and EUCIA are warmly acknowledged, as well as discussions with many colleagues from academia and industry interested in assessing the environmental impact of composites.

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